

Differential Privacy and the Survey Data Pipeline*

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1 Introduction

Differential privacy (DP) [8] has become the quasi-gold standard in recent years for data collection and dissemination whenever privacy or confidentiality is a concern. It offers formal (that is, mathematically quantifiable) privacy guarantees by bounding the influence that any single record of the database can have on the computed outputs. However, when working with survey data, there are additional complexities which typically do not arise in other settings. Moreover, the implications of using DP in the context of surveys have received little attention in the DP literature until recently. This led the U.S. Census Bureau to conclude in 2022 that “the science does not yet exist” to implement DP in its American Community Survey [13]. An expert panel convened by the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine reached a similar conclusion with respect to the Survey of Income and Program Participation [12].

In this paper, we focus on one of the challenges that arise in the survey context (see Drechsler and Bailie [7] for a review of other challenges): With surveys, data production is a multistage process. As such, there are various options for how and where to integrate DP in this pipeline, each of which come with their own advantages and disadvantages. Specifically, as we will illustrate, data custodians willing to adopt DP for their surveys need to address two important questions: Firstly, at what point in the pipeline should the DP mechanism start? And secondly, which of the earlier stages of the data pipeline should be considered invariant – i.e., should be treated as fixed – by DP? We will highlight the implications of these decisions and offer guidelines which settings statistical agencies should potentially adopt when implementing DP for their surveys.

2 The Survey Pipeline

The production of survey data is a complex multistage process (Figure 1). The design of a survey typically begins by conceiving the *target population*: the set of units that one wants to study. Once the target population has been defined, the *frame* is sourced. The frame is a register of units from which the sample will eventually be drawn. It must include sufficient contact information so that the sampled units can be surveyed. Although desirable, perfect alignment between the target population and the frame is not possible in most cases because errors will typically be made in the frame’s construction.

A *sample* is randomly drawn from the frame according to the survey’s *sampling design*: the probability distribution which specifies for every potential sample the chance that sample is selected. After sample selection, the statistical agency will solicit survey data from the sampled units. Most surveys, especially modern ones, suffer from nonresponse. This means only a subset of the sampled units will respond. Data collected from the responding sample are passed through a number

*Sections 1 to Section 3 are excerpts from the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) working paper, Drechsler and Bailie [7], which will also be published in the forthcoming NBER edited volume, Gong et al. [10].
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Figure 1: A *survey pipeline* consists of multiple steps.

of complex data processing steps before the survey outputs are computed and released. These data processing steps often include editing survey responses to correct errors; imputing missing answers to individual survey questions (“item nonresponse”) or to the entire survey questionnaire (“unit nonresponse”); and calculating multiple sets of survey weights for each record—to account for unequal probabilities of selection in the sampling design, to mitigate bias due to nonresponse patterns, and to calibrate survey data to auxiliary sources of information. (See Drechsler and Bailie [7] for further details on the survey pipeline.)

3 DP in the Survey Pipeline

There are two important considerations when integrating a DP mechanism into a data pipeline. Firstly, at what point in the pipeline should the DP mechanism start? And secondly, which of the earlier stages of the data pipeline should be considered invariant – i.e., should be treated as fixed – by DP? With survey pipelines, there are a number of possible options with respect to both considerations. In the option most commonly seen in the DP literature, the data-release mechanism starts at the end of the pipeline and performs just the last step – computing the survey outputs from the processed data – and none of the previous steps are taken as invariant. However, a mechanism could conceivably start at any point of the survey pipeline and incorporate all the steps that follow. Furthermore, any of the steps before the mechanism starts could conceivably be taken as invariant. Overall, this leads to up to 15 possible scenarios that need to be considered. Figure 3 highlights ten of these scenarios for illustration (the remaining five options would all start at the responding sample level). Before discussing the advantages and disadvantages of the different scenarios in the next section, a few general observations can be made: From a privacy perspective, it seems advantageous to start the DP mechanism as early as possible to benefit as much as possible from privacy amplification through subsampling [4]. Note that the data production pipeline consists of three sampling steps: beyond the classical sampling step, nonresponse can be treated as another subsampling step and even the frame can be seen as a random sample from the target population, if we model the probability of inclusion in the frame as a random variable. However, this privacy amplification can be nullified if the attacker knows that the record they are attacking is in the sample [2], a scenario that statistical agencies often need to consider in practice. On the other hand, any stage of the survey pipeline that should be part of the DP mechanism must first be fully “algorithmized” (that is, the process by which each of the stage’s possible inputs is transformed into one of its outputs must be completely and programmatically specified). A survey pipeline often includes a number of complex, ill-defined and human-intensive tasks, such as building the frame, choosing a sampling design, coding and editing. Because these tasks all usually require a degree of human judgment, they would be difficult to algorithmize.

Another downside of starting the DP mechanism earlier is the fact that it can complicate the computation of the cumulative privacy loss across multiple data-release mechanisms because DP’s composition theorems are not applicable when there is dependence between the mechanisms’ noise terms (which can happen, for example, when their sampling designs are dependent or when two noisy statistics are computed from the same sample) [2]. However, even if a data-release

Figure 2: 10 out of fifteen possible settings for a DP mechanism in the survey context. The red rectangulars indicate the starting point of the mechanism.

mechanism begins later in the survey pipeline so that some steps of the pipeline do not have to be incorporated in the mechanism, implementing DP still requires understanding those steps’ effect on the mechanism’s input data. For example, some imputation techniques replace missing records with copies of non-missing donor records. This means an individual survey respondent can contribute to multiple records in the post-imputation dataset. This complicates the appropriate definition of neighboring datasets: In the post-imputation dataset, changing a single record does not correspond to changing the data of one entity. In general, the later the DP mechanism begins, the more difficult it is to determine an appropriate notion of neighbors since steps earlier in the pipeline may introduce dependencies between dataset records.

These complexities demonstrate that there can be conflicting demands in deciding where a DP mechanism should start within the survey pipeline. (See Drechsler and Bailie [7] for further aspects that need to be considered.)

We now return to the question of which steps of the survey pipeline should DP take as invariant. DP assesses the privacy of a data-release mechanism by comparing the survey outputs’ distribution under pairs of counterfactual input datasets. By taking some of the steps of the survey pipeline as invariant, DP’s counterfactual comparisons are reduced to only those pairs of input datasets which share the same realization of the invariant steps. For example, suppose the steps in the survey pipeline which generate the population and the frame are taken as invariant and the data-release mechanism starts with the responding sample. Then DP only compares those responding samples (i.e. those counterfactual input datasets) which could have come from the same frame. Adding invariants will weaken the privacy guarantees provided by DP [1, 3, 11]. In general, the later the stage of the pipeline that is kept invariant, the greater the reduction in privacy. However, invariants may be justifiable when the output of the invariant steps can be considered as public knowledge (such as if the frame was sourced commercially rather than constructed from confidential information). Moreover, constraining some steps to be invariant has the advantage of reducing the sensitivity of survey weighted estimators and thereby decreasing the noise which must be added for privacy protection. We discuss this aspect in more detail in the next section.

4 Recommendations for DP in the Survey Context

In this section, we review the advantages and disadvantages of the fifteen possible settings for the DP mechanism and give recommendations on which settings should be preferred in practice.

Starting at the population level has the advantage that we can benefit from the “sampling” step when going from the population to the frame. However, the amplification effects will generally be negligible as high quality frames typically cover more than 95% of the target population. On the other hand, we would need to be able to fully “algorithmize” the generation of the sampling frame (an unrealistic assumption). Since starting at the population level offers no meaningful advantages over any of the other settings, we don’t recommend this choice.

Starting at the frame level has the advantage that the population can be treated as fixed and the amplification effects of sampling can be fully exploited. However, as Bun et al. [5] have shown,

amplification effects for the complex sampling designs that are used in practice tend to be small and as discussed above disappear completely if the attacker knows that a unit is included in the sample. This knowledge is not unrealistic in practice, as neighbors might observe that interviewers enter the house next door or survey respondents might post about their participation on social media. On the other hand, not fixing the frame has the severe drawback that the sensitivity of the analysis models can increase significantly. To account for the complex sampling designs it is common practice to weight each survey respondent with the inverse of the probability to be included in the sample when analyzing the survey data. For many survey designs, the probability of inclusion is data dependent, implying that changing one record in the data can change the weighting factor for each record in the sample. This has severe negative effects regarding the sensitivity of any statistic computed on the sample records. Thus, we generally do not recommend this setting unless the sampling design is not data dependent, which is rare in practice.

Starting at the sample level has the important advantage that it allows treating the frame as fixed and thus reducing the sensitivity of any statistic computed on the data. This advantage should outweigh the two negative effects of (i) losing the amplification effect from sampling which as discussed above is expected to be small and (ii) reducing the level of privacy by treating the frame as fixed. Note that fixing the frame limits the space of neighboring datasets to all samples that could have come from the same frame. While reducing the dataset space will clearly have a negative impact on the privacy guarantees that is not reflected in the privacy loss parameters of DP, it seems that the space should still be large enough to not significantly affect the actual level of privacy. We would Based on these discussions we identify the setting that starts the DP mechanism at the sample level and treats the frame as fixed as the most preferable option among all the settings discussed so far. Fully understanding the consequences of introducing invariants into the survey pipeline would be an interesting area of future research. We also note that starting at the sample level would also allow to benefit from the privacy amplification effect from nonresponse, at least in principle. However, in most cases it is unrealistic to assume that the response probability is constant across all units in the sample. We would therefore need to make strong assumptions how the response probability correlates with the survey attributes. A misspecified model would risk that we overstate the privacy guarantees from nonresponse.

The only advantage of **starting at the respondent level or later** seems to be that none of the previous steps in the survey pipeline need to be “algorithmizable”. However, this does not mean that the impacts of the previous steps need not be taken into account. These steps can have strong impacts on the sensitivity of the target analysis. For example, Das et al. [6] have shown that the sensitivity can increase linearly with the number of missing cases if missing values are imputed and DP is only taken into account when analyzing the imputed data. Better results are achievable if differentially private imputation routines are used. Thus, we currently don’t see any advantages of starting the DP mechanism at the respondent level or later. We strongly advise against treating the sample or any of the later stages as fixed as this might put strong constraints on the dataset space limiting the privacy achievable for any DP mechanism (see Gong and Meng [9] for a related discussion of the negative impacts of invariants).

5 Discussion

In this paper we discussed a conceptual framework for differential privacy for survey data. As the data collection process consists of multiple stages, statistical agencies have to decide at which stage of the pipeline the DP mechanism should start and which of the earlier stages should be considered invariant. We highlighted the advantages and disadvantages of the various settings. Based on previous research it seems that the setting that starts at the sample level and treats the frame as fixed offers an optimal balance between utility, privacy, and practicability.

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